

Helping people access data fast and efficiently

OPeNDAP Services for Data Users

Summary

OPeNDAP streamlines remote data access by allowing users to stream subsets of data from larger datasets, minimizing transfer costs and boosting performance. By using simple URLs, users can subset data, access only relevant variables, and use familiar languages like Python and R, and tools like Jupyter notebooks and GIS software, without needing to download entire files or reformat data. Originally made by scientists for scientists, OPeNDAP's technologies support data exploration, model prototyping, and scalable pre-processing using innovations like lazy metadata-loading and DMR++ for fast, metadata-driven indexing. By making remote data feel local, OPeNDAP offers a powerful solution for modern, cloud-based data analysis. This document details the benefits of using OPeNDAP's technology, and how it works.

Access data remotely with OPeNDAP

Gone are the days when you needed to physically access data, such as by sending hard drives in the mail or traveling in-person to a data center. **OPeNDAP helps users stream data**, so data providers and their users can save time, money, and hassle.

Here is how the OPeNDAP approach works for a data user (Figure 1):

Step 1. The user starts by choosing an appropriate analysis tool such as Matlab, Jupyter notebook, ArcGIS, R, et cetera. For example, an analyst might use Jupyter notebook and Xarray to explore the presence of *Chlorophyll* over a region in the North Atlantic.

Step 2. Within the analysis software (Jupyter notebook in this example), the user requests a subset of data from a larger dataset that has already been made available via OPeNDAP's tools. For example, the analyst might stream data from NASA's Earthdata repository where an OPeNDAP server is located. Such a request takes the form of a URL that is customized to the subsetting requirements identified by the analyst.

Step 3: When data are streamed to the user, the data are stored locally on the user's computer while the data are being used and analysis is occurring. For example, the analyst might use visualization tools within Jupyter notebook to present maps of *Chlorophyll*. When they are satisfied with data analysis, the analyst can save the results, and the data are automatically removed when the analysis tool stops.

Importantly: The entire source dataset was never transferred to the user's computer. Instead, only the subset of data they care about was transferred for a short time during the streaming process, saving them time, labor, and space in their computer.

What's happening under the hood: Xarray appends constraints expressions to the OPeNDAP URL following OPeNDAP's protocol (called the "DAP") and sends that request to the OPeNDAP server (called Hyrax), which is housed at the data repository. The server subsets the data, and streams only the requested information over the web.

Figure 1. A typical workflow for a data scientist accessing data using OPeNDAP.

Stream only the data you need

Datasets are often composed of numerous variables and metadata¹. Downloading entire datasets can mean wasted hours of a data user's time, since they typically only need a few variables, subsets of those variables, and basic metadata to do their work.

OPeNDAP provides technology that allows users to subset data by requesting just the data they need. Subsetting minimizes data transfer costs and improves performance, especially in cloud-hosted environments. By being able to slice up data quickly, data users can easily explore data and prototype different analysis models. With OPeNDAP's "lazy metadata-loading" approach, users only get the most essential metadata associated with their datasets, enabling fewer reads of data for higher efficiency.

Get data quickly

With today's datasets quickly growing in volume and complexity, reading entire datasets to identify which parts a user actually needs can be clunky, slow, and unnecessary.

OPeNDAP speeds up remote data access by using data mapping technology called DMR++ (Dataset Metadata Response++). By organizing and documenting metadata in a compact file, DMR++ acts like a map to tell a system where data are. Such technology is how OPeNDAP accurately subsets and streams large datasets in a matter of minutes.

Use any analysis tool

There is so much to learn when working with new data, and the last thing that people want to do is learn a new analysis tool.

With OPeNDAP, people use analysis tools they are already familiar with, including Python, MATLAB, R, Panoply, and ArcGIS. A person requests their analysis tool of choice to construct a custom OPeNDAP web URL that is used to stream subsets of data over the cloud. In this way, datasets look and behave like local files.

¹ Metadata are data about data. They provide context and meaning for data by describing things like where the data came from, where and how data were collected, and how they are managed.

No need to re-format data

A data analyst working with data locally must often spend days of their valuable time re-organizing and re-formatting the data before they can begin to use it. OPeNDAP helps avoid much of this work by providing technology that mitigates the need to re-format data, while enabling performant access and processing.

Users don't have to worry about what format the original data are in. Instead, OPeNDAP exposes the structure of the data so different analysis tools can work with them. When a user requests data using the OPeNDAP approach, data are streamed back in simple standardized formats (like a binary stream), so the data are immediately usable in an analysis tool without the need to convert the format.

For example, NASA's [Earthdata system](#) sought to store their existing geospatial HDF4/5 data files on the cloud. They also wanted people to be able to access just parts of the datasets without downloading them, similar to how cloud-based Zarr and Parquet data formats behave. However, using such formats would have required complex reformatting of all the legacy data files into the new cloud data formats. To avoid all of this reformatting, they instead chose to implement OPeNDAP's solution to stream data.

In today's data-driven world, fast and efficient access to data is essential. OPeNDAP's advanced streaming technology enables users to access and work with large, complex datasets quickly, easily, and cost-effectively—without the need to download or reformat.

About OPeNDAP

OPeNDAP is a 501(c)3 not-for-profit corporation and the developer of a suite of open source software tools, including the Hyrax data server and DMR++. OPeNDAP's software facilitates efficient remote data exchange by allowing users to stream subsets of data from large datasets and use data without needing to download and reformat data. OPeNDAP's state-of-the-art technology provides fast and convenient access to data—especially for data stored in the cloud, helping data providers and data users save time and money. Most well-known for their long-time support of NASA's Earth science data system, OPeNDAP's technology is applicable to any data-intensive domain or sector.

To learn more about if OPeNDAP is the right solution for your business, please reach out to us at support@opendap.org.